

Synthesis and spectral characterization of 2-(substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/-2-thiones

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Abstract : 2-(Substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/-2-thiones (3-10) were synthesized in a two step process. Condensation of equimolar quantities of 3-aminopropanol (1) with phosphorous oxychloride/thiophosphoryl chloride in dry THF in presence of Et₃N to afford the corresponding intermediate 2-chloro-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-one/-2-thione (2). In the next step 2 reacted *in situ* with various phenols and aromatic amines in dry THF and TEA to obtain the title compounds. Analytical data, IR, ¹H, ¹³C, ³¹P and Mass spectral data have been discussed and supported all the structures.

Keywords : 2-(Substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/-2-thiones, 2-chloro-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-one/-2-thione, IR, NMR, Mass.

Introduction

Synthesis of six-membered phosphorus heterocycles containing O, N as heteroatoms and P as P=O (S) has been the subject of research, ever since cyclophosphamide, [2-bis-2-(2-chloroethyl)amino]-2H-[1,3,2]-oxazaphosphorinane-2-oxide was discovered as an anti-cancer drug¹. Zimmer and Sill² prepared the pyridine analog of benzodiazaphosphole-2-oxide and this compound also proved to be an effective anti-cancer agent.

Takamizawa *et al.*³ synthesized 2-[bis-(2-chloroethyl)amino]-5,6-dihydro-2H-1,3,2-oxazaphosphorin-4-(3H)-one-2-oxide. This compound was also found to be useful as an anti-cancer drug. With the basic idea of using organophosphorus compounds as antimetabolites in cancer chemotherapy, a number of phosphorus nitrogen mustard compounds have been synthesized. In the present investigation, a series of new 2-(substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/-2-thiones (3-10) were successfully synthesized.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of 2-(substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/-2-thiones (3-10) was accomplished in a two-step process. The synthetic route involves the condensation of equimolar quantities of 3-aminopropanol (1) with phosphorus oxychloride/thiophosphoryl chloride in dry THF, in the presence of triethylamine (TEA) at 30-40 °C temperature to afford the corresponding intermediate 2-chloro-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-one/-2-thione (2). The progress of the reaction was followed by TLC (hexane-ethyl acetate, 7 : 3) at regular intervals. In the second step, the intermediate compound (2) was reacted *in situ* with various phenols and aromatic amines of high molecular weights in dry THF in the presence of TEA to obtain the title compounds 3-10 in optimum yields. The triethylamine hydrochloride formed in the reaction being insoluble in THF is separated by filtration. The second step of the reaction was completed at reflux temperature with vigorous stirring for 6-8 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (hexane-ethyl acetate,

7 : 3). THF was found to be suitable solvent since the reactants readily dissolved in it. The crude products obtained after removing the solvent from the filtrate in rotavaporator were purified by column chromatography on silica gel, using hexane-ethyl acetate (3 : 2) as an eluent. These compounds melted in the range of 182–200 °C and their yields were in the range of 54–71%.

Compd.	X	R
3	O	
4	O	
5	O	
6	S	
7	S	
8	S	
9	O	
10	O	

Scheme 1

The infrared spectral study of all the title compounds (3-10) has been made and the data are correlated with the

main functional groups. The infrared spectral data are given in the Table 1. The compounds 3 to 5, 9 and 10 showed characteristic absorption bands for P=O^{4,5} functional group in the region 1225–1233 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of phosphoryl group in them. The appearance of P=O absorption in the lower region indicates that the phosphoryl group is involved in hydrogen bonding in these compounds. The compounds 6-8 exhibited characteristic infrared absorption bands in the region 771–773 cm⁻¹ for P=S stretching frequencies^{4,6}. The compounds 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10 exhibited characteristic infrared absorption bands for P-O-(C_{aryl}) and (P)-O-C_{aryl} functional groups in the region 939–983 and 1201–1211 cm⁻¹ respectively. The absorption bands in these regions undoubtedly confirm the presence of P-O-C_{aromatic} group in these compounds^{5,7}. The compounds 3-10 exhibited characteristic infrared absorption bands for P-O-C_{aliphatic} functional group^{4,8} in the region 1013–1046 cm⁻¹. The compounds 3-10 exhibited characteristic infrared absorption bands in the region 3290–3386 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of P-NH⁴ in these compounds.

¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR spectra of 3-10 were recorded and interpreted, based on additivity rules, intensity of signals and some model compounds. The proton NMR chemical shifts of the compounds (3-10) are given in the Table 2. The aromatic protons of 2-(substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/2-thiones showed a complex multiplet in the region δ 6.64–8.26. The N-H proton (endocyclic) in these compounds exhibited a doublet in the region δ 2.33–3.33 and exocyclic NH proton in 5 and 9 resonated as a singlet in the region δ 4.20–4.36. All other protons are resonated in the expected region. The ¹³C NMR spectral data of these compounds are presented in the Table 3. C-4 carbons are resonated in the region δ 37.5–45.8. C-5 carbons are showed signals in the range of δ 27.4–29.7. C-6 carbons are resonated in the region δ 53.4–62.4. Aromatic ring carbons attached to P-O or P-NH are resonated in down field region. All other aromatic carbons are resonated in the expected regions. Tertiary carbons in 10 are resonated at δ 34.7 and 44.2 respectively. ³¹P NMR spectral data for all the title compounds 3-10 are given in Table 2. ³¹P NMR chemical shifts⁹ of these compounds appeared in the region 3.51–7.93 ppm. The LCMS data of compounds 3, 6, 7, 8 are presented in the Table 4.

Note

Table 1. Synthetic, physical and IR data of 2-(substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/-2-thiones (3-10)

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Elemental analysis (%) :			P=O	P=S	P-O-C _(aro)			P-NH
				Found (Calcd.)					P-O	O-C	P-O-C _(ali)	
				C	H	N						
3	182-184	55	C ₉ H ₉ PO ₃ Cl ₃ N	34.21 (34.13)	2.91 (2.81)	4.49 (4.43)	1226	-	947	1202	1029	3290
4	191-193	62	C ₉ H ₉ PO ₃ Cl ₃ N	34.52 (34.13)	2.90 (2.87)	4.38 (4.43)	1225	-	944	1201	1024	3340
5	196-198	58	C ₉ H ₁₀ PO ₂ Cl ₃ N ₂	34.14 (34.24)	3.17 (3.20)	8.92 (8.88)	1230	-	-	-	1036	3322
6	192-194	67	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ PSO ₂ N	55.82 (55.88)	4.97 (5.06)	5.04 (5.02)	-	773	975	1206	1039	3380
7	196-198	54	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ PSO ₂ N ₂	51.53 (51.40)	4.65 (4.68)	10.04 (10.00)	-	771	952	1411	1027	3362
8	184-186	71	C ₉ H ₁₁ PSO ₂ NBr	35.03 (35.06)	3.57 (3.60)	4.63 (4.55)	-	772	952	1207	1020	3304
9	198-200	66	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ PN ₂ O ₂	59.77 (59.77)	5.73 (5.77)	10.77 (10.69)	1233	-	-	-	1046	3386
10	188-190	62	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ PNO ₃	62.89 (62.73)	8.59 (8.68)	4.28 (4.31)	1225	-	939	1202	1013	33354

Table 2. ¹H and ³¹P NMR spectral data^{a,b} of 2-(substituted)-1,3,2λ⁵-oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/2-thiones (3-10)

Compd.	Ar-H	(N-H)			N-H		³¹ P NMR ^c	
		endocyclic	4 (CH ₂)	5 (CH ₂)	6 (CH ₂)	exocyclic		<i>t</i> -Butyl
3	7.16-7.26 (2H, m)	2.74 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 7.2, 7.6 Hz)	3.34-3.40 (2H, m)	1.18-1.33 (2H, m)	5.12-5.82 (2H, m)	-	-	3.72
4	6.64-7.30 (2H, m)	2.82 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 6.8, 7.2 Hz)	3.40-3.83 (2H, m)	1.25-1.35 (2H, m)	5.30-5.76 (2H, m)	-	-	7.93
5	6.91-7.71 (2H, m)	2.32 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 6.8, 8.0 Hz)	3.30-3.44 (2H, m)	1.38-1.41 (2H, m)	5.32-5.46 (2H, m)	4.36 (d, <i>J</i> 9.6 Hz)	-	4.24
6	7.32-8.26 (7H, m)	2.74 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 7.2, 7.2 Hz)	3.34-3.52 (2H, m)	1.25-1.50 (2H, m)	5.27-5.79 (2H, m)	-	-	3.62
7	7.05-7.55 (3H, m)	2.78 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 6.4, 7.2 Hz)	3.45-3.48 (2H, m)	1.01-1.65 (2H, m)	4.73-5.21 (2H, m)	-	-	4.82
8	6.74-7.57 (4H, m)	2.64 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 7.0, 7.4 Hz)	3.01-3.88 (2H, m)	1.15-1.61 (2H, m)	5.17-5.67 (2H, m)	-	-	6.27
9	6.76-7.77 (7H, m)	2.42 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 6.4, 9.6 Hz)	3.24-4.10 (2H, m)	1.24-1.35 (2H, m)	5.28-5.78 (2H, m)	4.20 (d, <i>J</i> 11.2 Hz)	-	3.51
10	6.71-7.25 (3H, m)	2.86 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 6.4, 9.2 Hz)	3.44-3.52 (2H, m)	1.44-1.22 (2H, m)	5.26-5.72 (2H, m)	-	1.30 (4') (9H, s), 1.27 (2') (9H, s)	5.01

^aChemical shifts in δ and *J* (Hz) value given in parenthesis. ^bRecorded in CDCl₃.

^cChemical shifts in ppm referenced to 85% H₃PO₄.

Table 3. ^{13}C NMR data of 2-(substituted)-1,3,2 λ^5 -oxazaphosphinan-2-ones/-2-thiones (3-10)

Compd.	Chemical shifts (ppm)
3	45.6 (C-4), 29.7 (C-5), 58.2 (C-6), 142.2 (C-1'), 127.7 (C-2'/C-6'), 130.0 (C-3'/C-5'), 129.7 (C-4')
4	40.9 (C-4), 27.6 (C-5), 61.2 (C-6), 154.8 (C-1'), 124.2 (C-2'), 133.4 (C-3'), 126.9 (C-4'), 131.0 (C-5'), 120.0 (C-6')
5	41.1 (C-4), 27.4 (C-5), 53.4 (C-6), 142.8 (C-1'), 124.2 (C-2' and C-4'), 131.5 (C-3'), 131.1 (C-5'), 119.6 (C-6')
6	41.2 (C-4), 27.4 (C-5), 53.5 (C-6), 108.4 (C-1'), 152.8 (C-2'), 119.1 (C-3'), 127.3 (C-4'), 124.1 (C-5'), 126.1 (C-6'), 126.4 (C-7'), 124.9 (C-8'), 134.7 (C-9'), 127.6 (C-10')
7	37.5 (C-4), 29.0 (C-5), 59.0 (C-6), 142.5 (C-1'), 129.1 (C-2'), 127.5 (C-3'), 126.3 (C-4'), 137.1 (C-5'), 121.8 (C-6'), 146.7 (C-7'), 129.0 (C-8'), 153.4 (C-9')
8	39.9 (C-4), 28.6 (C-5), 57.9 (C-6), 151.9 (C-1'), 117.5 (C-2' and C-6'), 132.9 (C-3' and C-5'), 114.9 (C-4')
9	41.6 (C-4), 29.7 (C-5), 62.4 (C-6), 146.2 (C-1'), 109.7 (C-2'), 126.6 (C-3'), 120.9 (C-4'), 128.5 (C-5'), 126.3 (C-6'), 125.7 (C-7'), 120.9 (C-8'), 134.2 (C-9'), 124.8 (C-10')
10	45.8 (C-4), 29.6 (C-5), 53.4 (C-6), 142.1 (C-1'), 135.0 (C-2'), 123.7 (C-3'), 139.6 (C-4'), 123.3 (C-5'), 116.0 (C-6')

Table 4. LC mass spectral data

Compd.	m/z (%)
3	305 (3), 304 (5), 303 (100), 289 (20), 271 (27), 265 (30), 247 (27)
6	280 [100, (M+1) $^+$], 252 (6), 235 (2), 222 (2)
7	281 [45, (M+1) $^+$], 249 (50), 175 (30), 148 (40), 119 (80), 87 (100)
8	310 [52, (M+2) $^+$], 309 [54, (M+1) $^+$], 281 (12), 204 (5)

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR 1000 spectrophotometer. The ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P NMR spectra were taken on Bruker ACF NMR spectrophotometer operating at 400, 100 and 161.89 MHz respec-

tively in CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ and were referenced to TMS (^1H and ^{13}C) and 85% H_3PO_4 (^{31}P). Mass spectral data were collected on LCMS-2010A, Shimadzu spectrometer.

Preparation of 2-(naphthyloxy)-1,3,2 λ^5 -oxazaphosphinan-2-thione (6) :

Thiophosphoryl chloride (0.31 g, 0.002 mol) in 20 mL of dry tetrahydrofuran (THF) was added drop wise over a period of 20 min to a stirred solution of 3-amino-propanol (0.15 g, 0.002 mol) and triethylamine (TEA) (0.404 g, 0.004 mol) in 20 mL of dry tetrahydrofuran at 0 $^\circ\text{C}$. After the addition, the temperature of the reaction mixture was raised to 40 $^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred for about 6 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC analysis (*n*-hexane-ethyl acetate, 3 : 1), at different regular intervals. After cooling the reaction mixture, β -naphthol (0.29 g, 0.002 mol), TEA (0.202 g, 0.002 mol) were added to the reaction mixture *in situ* and the reaction mixture was refluxed for about 6 h. The completion of the reaction was ascertained by TLC analysis (*n*-hexane-ethyl acetate, 3 : 1). The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was removed by filtration and the solvent was removed from the filtrate in a rota-evaporator. The residue was washed with water and recrystallized from chloroform-hexane (1 : 3). The recrystallized solid was further purified by column chromatography using silica gel (60-120 mesh) as adsorbent using hexane and ethyl acetate (2 : 1) as an eluent.

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